

WAYS TO DEVELOP E-COMMERCE IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. This article presents opinions on the role and importance of e-commerce, its development stages in Uzbekistan, and future development opportunities. Also, the evaluation of its capabilities and the determination of development prospects are highlighted.

Keywords: e-commerce, "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy, electronic payment, information technologies, new economic relations, global Internet, COVID-19.

Introduction. First and foremost, in order to develop a new Uzbekistan, create promising projects, organize sustainable economic processes in our country, the head of our state has set a goal to take a bold step towards development, with special attention to each area.

In this regard, the Decree No. PF-6079 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoyev dated October 5, 2020 “On approval of the “Digital Uzbekistan – 2030” strategy and measures for its effective implementation” In order to develop the system of electronic commerce and electronic payments, the following activities are carried out: development of remote banking services through the introduction of information and communication technologies, including remote customer identification systems; to improve and update the legal basis of e-commerce development, as well as existing standards and e-commerce

regulations, to comply with international e-commerce standards and modern information security requirements; development of digital infrastructure, increasing the scope and scope of connecting to e-commerce platforms from personal digital equipment by further increasing the coverage and speed of the global information network of mobile and wired Internet, etc.

Literature review. First of all, let's talk about e-commerce, or online commerce, which is the process of buying and selling products and services over the Internet, and it is an important field that is growing with the development of the Internet and becoming a part of our daily lives. Electronic commerce is used to describe commercial activity on the Internet. It provides an opportunity to purchase, sell, provide service, and conduct marketing activities using a computer network. To date, e-commerce has carried out extensive work in the economy of Uzbekistan, and the ground has been created for studying the current situation, problems and prospects in the country.

According to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated September 29, 2022 “ON ELECTRONIC COMMERCE” No. ORQ-792, the main principles of electronic commerce are as follows:

- freedom to carry out business activities in the field of e-commerce;
- voluntary conclusion of contracts in electronic commerce;
- equality of conditions for participation in electronic commerce;
- protection of the rights and legal interests of e-commerce entities;
- ensuring the appropriate level of quality of goods (works, services);
- openness and transparency of processes in electronic commerce;
- ensuring information security in electronic commerce.

Analysis and results. Today, the basis of the achievements in the economy, especially in the field of modern marketing, is the highly developed and effective use of various segments of information technologies. The economy of Uzbekistan is certainly not an exception. As a clear example, a number of segments of

information technologies, such as data transmission networks, Internet information resources and electronic document exchange between them, Internet marketing systems, business and commerce are developing steadily. For Uzbekistan, the development of information technologies is of great importance in ensuring new economic relations.

In the development of e-commerce, the level of development of telecommunication infrastructure in the country and the level of Internet connection, as well as the presence of websites in enterprises, are among the important factors.

When setting up an electronic business, it is important to consider the following organizational principles:

- Determination of the profit rate as an objective function in the conditions of financing of extended reproduction, which implies conducting marketing research of consumer demand and measures to stimulate the sale of mass-produced products and services;
- Carrying out the company's innovation policy (introduction of new production, information and management technologies) to increase the company's competitiveness and tolerance to changes in the external environment;
- Flexibility in the organization of business processes provided by a reasonable technological, assortment, price, sales and personnel policy;
- Objective assessment of business risk and forecasting the market situation using modern management theory and mathematical modeling;
- Computerization of business processes, as well as use of modern technical and software for storing and protecting business information.

E-commerce retail shows that COVID-19 has had a significant impact on e-commerce, with sales expected to reach \$6.5 trillion by 2023. It can be concluded that due to the virus, the overall e-commerce is growing rapidly. The coronavirus has forced customers to use the internet and make it a habit in their daily lives. In

addition, many challenges faced by sellers in e-commerce have increased, such as extended delivery times, difficulties in managing traffic, social distancing and lockdowns. The shipping and delivery process is much slower now, but people are still buying because there is no other alternative. So people are switching to technology because of the virus.

As a result of the gradual development of Uzbekistan's economy, the importance of new principles of conducting business activities, especially electronic commerce, has greatly increased. By now, every internet user has tried to understand the meaning of the word e-commerce. On average, 1.5 - 2 trillion per year in the US markets related to such activity, which has not yet had time to build its long history. Funds are converted in US dollars.

E-commerce can be seen as one of the most promising areas of business activity in the current development of New Uzbekistan. According to industry experts, the republic has all the necessary conditions and resources for the development of e-commerce. Among them, the increase in the level of computer literacy of the population, the spread of high-quality Internet with low traffic prices throughout the country, etc.

In fact, one of the main factors in the development of e-commerce is the use of the global Internet. From a technical point of view, the Internet of the Republic of Uzbekistan is ready to develop e-commerce in the country. Rapid growth of the number of Internet users and development of information and communication technologies is observed in our country. This leads to a significant expansion of the scope of commercial communications through the Internet. But this does not indicate that electronic commerce is highly developed, that is, it is necessary to improve the communication and telecommunication infrastructure that ensures information security in electronic forms of mutual cooperation between business entities. Also, revision and coordination of the current legal framework in the field of e-commerce, development of online applications supporting e-commerce

for business, promotion aimed at increasing e-commerce literacy among citizens of the country continuous holding of events, development of the electronic money market and support for the popularization of electronic wallets serve to further develop electronic commerce.

In general, one thing is clear that the share of e-commerce in the country's economy will continuously increase in the near future. It has a positive effect not only on the activities of economic sectors and entrepreneurs, but also on the standard of living of the population.

Summary. Thus, it should be emphasized that the opportunities for the development of e-commerce in Uzbekistan are growing year by year. Its development will create opportunities for our national producers to open new markets, find new customers, and prevent excess costs and waste. Following the chosen and current path of e-commerce development will make the economy of Uzbekistan one of the leading representatives of the world market in the future. Choosing the right way to solve the problems of electronic commerce in Uzbekistan is reflected in the well-being of the people, the progress of our society, and our economic development.

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